

PIE NEWS PLATFORM RELEASE (I, II, III, IV, V)

D4.3

Project:	PIE News – Poverty, Income, and Employment News (H2020-ICT-2015)
Duration:	1st July 2016 – 30th June 2019 (36 months)
Contract Number:	Grant Agreement Number 687922
Partners:	University of Trento, Basic Income Network Italy, Centre for Peace Studies, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Stichting Dyne.org, Abertay University, Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute
Document Number:	D4.3
Contractual Date:	30/6/2019
Work Package:	WP4
Distribution / Type:	Public / Demonstration
Version:	Final
Total Number of Pages:	38
File:	PIE_D4.3_FIN
Authors:	Pietro Benedetto Molini, Stefano De Paoli, Daniel Rough

In this document we describe the different components of the Commonfare platform, highlighting their features of novelty and giving high level insights about how they have been implemented and integrated with the other technological components that have been developed during the project.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this document is to illustrate the main characteristics of the Commonfare.net platform, the main and more visible technological outcome of the PIE News/Commonfare project.

This document is divided in two parts. The first is completely focused on the features of Commonfare.net, and goes through all the main components that have been developed, namely the Commoners, the Stories, the Commoncoin, the Groups and the Group Currencies. Further, focus is given to those elements of the platform that required a work of integration, like in the case of the Social Wallet API and the Commonshare.

The second part of this report is dedicated to giving more details about the Commonshare Toolkit, from the theoretical and conceptual aspects to its actual implementation and integration into the platform.

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

DATE	VERSION	AUTHOR	SUMMARY OF CHANGES
05/06/2019	V0.1	Pietro Benedetto Molini	Document creation based on D4.1
08/06/2019	V0.2	Stefano De Paoli	Added section on Commonshare
14/06/2019	V0.3	Pietro Benedetto Molini	Finalised for internal review
21/06/2019	V0.4	Pietro Benedetto Molini	Revised after internal review

CONTRIBUTORS

FIRST NAME	LAST NAME	ORGANIZATION	CONTRIBUTION
Pietro Benedetto	Molini	Fondazione Bruno Kessler	Author
Stefano	De Paoli	Abertay University	Author
Daniel	Rough	Abertay University	Author
Peter	Lyle	M-ITI	Internal Reviewer
Sandro	Gobetti	BIN	Internal Reviewer

ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
R1	Release 1 of Commonfare.net - Information Hub in Annex 1 Language
R2	Release 2 of Commonfare.net (this encompasses R2.0, R2.1 and R2.1+) - Stories Hub in Annex 1 Language
R3	Release 3 of Commonfare.net - Networking Hub in Annex 1 Language
R4	Release 4 of Commonfare.net
WPx	Work Package X (e.g. WP4 refers to 'Work Package 4' and the interaction design and platform development work)
Dx,y	Deliverable report X.Y (X refers to the Work Package responsible, Y refers to the report number, e.g. D3.2 is Deliverable Report 2 from Work Package 3)
AU	Abertay University (Scotland, UK)
BIN	Basic Income Network Italy
CMS	Centre for Peace Studies (Croatia)
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler (Italy)
DYNE	Stitching Dyne.org (the Netherlands)
MdC	Museu da Crise (the Netherlands)
UNITN	University of Trento (Italy)
MITI	Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute (Portugal)
Mx	Month X of the Commonfare project
SWAPI	Social Wallet API
©	Oltrino

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	2
Document Revision History	3
Contributors	4
Acronyms	5
Table of Contents	6
List Of Figures	6
1. The Commonfare.net Platform	7
1.1 Commoners	8
1.1.1 Conversations and notifications	9
1.1.2 Anonymity	10
1.2 Stories	12
1.2.1 Story Builder	13
1.2.2 Comments	16
1.2.3 Recommended Stories	16
1.3 Commoncoin	17
1.3.1 Commonplace	18
1.3.2 Basic income and implementation notes	19
1.4 Groups	20
1.4.1 Group currency	21
1.5 Santacoin and Oltrino	22
1.6 Integration and Deployment	25
1.6.1 Group Currency architecture	26
1.7 Releases	27
1.7.1 Release 3	27
1.7.2 Release 4 and Final release	29
2. The Commonshare Toolkit	30
2.1 Modifications for dynamic, weighted networks	32
2.2 Summary	33
2.3 Implementation	34
2.4 Preliminary parsing	34
2.5 Platform integration	37

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE	TITLE	PAGE
1	The Commoner's profile and the visualisation of the Commonshare	9
2	A conversation between two commoners, with the notification badge and the list of Notifications	10
3	The Welcome page as it appeared in R2	11
4	The message that pops up when the user clicks our 'Share' button	11
5	The top part of a Story, as viewed on mobile and desktop screen	12
6	The WYSIWYG editor	14
7	The Story Builder in action	15
8	An example of Recommended Stories	16
9	The Commoncoin wallet and the transaction flow	18
10	Creation of a new Listing and a Listing page	19
11	The © wallet of a Customer and the activation page	24
12	Architecture of Commonfare.net	25
13	Commonfare with Group Currency	27
14	Centrality measures	31
15	Commonfare interactions for computation of the commonshare and k-core algorithm	32
16	GEXF for the Commonshare	34
17	Commonshare k-core decomposition	34
18	Algorithm for weighted calculation used for Commonshare	36
19	Normalisation of the Commonshare	37

1. THE COMMONFARE.NET PLATFORM

The Commonfare platform - <https://commonfare.net> - is the main technological outcome of the PIE News/Commonfare project. During the three years of the project UNITN has led the design of the platform, and FBK has led its development, implementation, and integration with the other technological components developed by DYNE and AU, namely the Social Wallet API and the Commonshare Toolkit.

In order to give a general overview of the components of the Commonfare platform, in this section we start our description from the Commoners and the Stories, respectively the people who use Commonfare.net, and the main content that they create on it, then we detail the Commoncoin, i.e. the currency available to all the Commoners, and the Groups. We then give an overview of how the two experiences of public usage of the digital currencies - Santacoin and Oltrino (©) - were carried out from a technical point of view, and finally we provide insights about the backend of Commonfare.net. The final section provides an overview of the work done by FBK, listed in the form of backlog items.

1.1 COMMONERS

In Commonfare.net we refer to people who join the platform and use it to write Stories, discuss with others, exchange Commoncoins, and so forth *Commoners*.

Commoners have a public profile with a chosen name, picture, description, and tags, which includes a list of all the Groups they are a member of, and the Stories the Commoner has published. The left image in Figure 1 shows the Commoner's profile on a mobile screen.

From R4, the main element of the Commoner's profile is the Commoner's activity on the platform, which we represent using the **Commonshare**, a 'metric for reputation' we developed for the purposes of Commonfare.net. More details about the Commonshare are given in the final section of this document, whereas the underlying research was carried out as part of WP3 research activities (ended M15) and is described in D3.1 and especially in D3.2.

FIGURE 1. THE COMMONER'S PROFILE AND THE VISUALISATION OF THE COMMONSHARE

The right image in Figure 1 shows the visualisation of the Commonshare as it is visible on the Commoner's profile, as visualised on a desktop screen. On the right there is the value of the Commonshare over time, drawn in different colors to highlight the different contributions to the Commonfare. The left part is the donut visualisation of the same information, but specific for a particular time frame (2 weeks). The design and evaluation of the visualisation are described in D5.3 in more details. The Commonshare is a metric which is the result of a combination of these types of contributions to the platform:

- social: contribution to interaction, for example a Commoner had conversations with other Commoners or has commented a Story
- story: contribution to content, for example the Commoner has posted one or more Stories
- transactions: contribution through sharing and distribution of Commoncoin. Transaction contributions are made by sending or receiving Commoncoin.

In the rest of this document we explain all these parts of Commonfare.net and how a Commoner can make use of them.

1.1.1 Conversations and notifications

Commoners can interact with each other using a private chat system embedded in the platform: on the Commoner's profile a button allows another Commoner to start a conversation with him/her, or to continue the conversation that the two Commoners already started. When a new message is delivered to any of the Commoner's conversations, a notification appears on the top-right part of the page. Notifications appear also for other activities and events (i.e. comments on content, transactions, etc.) and they are collected in a single page, as shown in the right image of Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. A CONVERSATION BETWEEN TWO COMMONERS, WITH THE NOTIFICATION BADGE (LEFT) AND THE LIST OF NOTIFICATIONS (RIGHT)

Notifications can be either *read* or *unread*, and they are highlighted in the latter case. The interaction that the Commoner has with Notifications varies according to the kind of Notification: for example, by clicking on a Notification related to a new Message in a Conversation, the Commoner is led to that Conversation, while if the Notification is about a Transaction, the Commoner is led to her/his Wallet (details about Transactions and Wallets are provided further in this document)

1.1.2 Anonymity

A very important aspect of Commonfare.net is the anonymity of the Commoners. Online anonymity is a crucial feature that came out clearly from pilot research and codesign activities (D2.1) and that we have been implementing since R2. For this reason we do not require that the email address is confirmed upon registration, which implies that the email used by the person can be real, temporary, or even fake.

Moreover, during registration, the new Commoner gets a unique randomly generated name that can be later changed in the 'Edit profile' section. After registration, the new Commoner arrives on a Welcome page that explains why he/she has got that name, along with a brief introduction to some of the main features of the platform.

FIGURE 3. THE WELCOME PAGE AS IT APPEARED IN R2

To further ensure anonymity of both Commoners and visitors of the platform, we do not use any 'social button' (like those by Facebook, Google, Twitter, Pinterest, etc.) on our pages. These buttons allow who clicks them to immediately share the URL of the page on the related social network, and they use tracking cookies even when they are not tapped/clicked¹.

On Commonfare.net we developed a simple and anonymous way for sharing content to other sites, while avoiding the use of embedded iFrames and Cookies (and other mechanisms) that track user activity. When our 'Share' button is clicked, a message like the one in Figure 4 appears, prompting the user to copy the URL of the page with just one click, so he/she can later paste it on any social networking platform.

FIGURE 4. THE MESSAGE THAT POPS UP WHEN THE USER CLICKS OUR 'SHARE' BUTTON

Finally, to keep and analyse usage statistics of Commonfare.net, we do not track the visits by means of an external tracking systems (e.g. Google Analytics), instead we use an internal instance of

¹ See <https://www.facebook.com/help/206635839404055> for Facebook

Matomo² (an open source web analytics tool, previously known as Piwik) whose data are accessible only by some members of the consortium.

1.2 STORIES

Stories are the main and more visible type of content that Commoners can create on Commonfare.net, and that any person can read and share. In fact, all the Stories on Commonfare.net are public, and anyone can interact with them using Comments (further details in section 1.2.2).

A Story is similar to a post in most classic blogging platforms, like Wordpress or Medium, and it is composed of:

- title, in multiple languages
- rich text body, in multiple languages
- images
- videos, embedded from the most popular video platforms
- tags
- metadata: place (where the Story takes place), author (Commoner or Group), date of creation, available languages.

The left part of Figure 5 shows how a Story appears on a mobile phone: the title is on top, followed by the tags and a box which contains the Story's metadata; the actual content starts afterwards. The same Story viewed on a normal screen is depicted in the right part of Figure 5.

FIGURE 5. THE TOP PART OF A STORY, AS VIEWED ON MOBILE AND DESKTOP SCREEN

² See Matomo official website <https://matomo.org/>

At the time of writing, Stories can be of three different categories: Commoners' Voices, Welfare Provisions, Tutorials. We used to have another category of Stories - Good Practices - that have been merged into Commoners' Voices in R4.

The categorisation of the Stories is done automatically by Commonfare.net based on either the author or the tags or both. For example, a Story becomes a Welfare Provision when the author is a member of the PIE News Consortium and the story has some specific tags, namely 'Welfare Provisions' and one of 'Misure di Welfare', 'Socijalna Zaštita', 'Sociale Voorziening' (i.e. the Italian, Croatian, and Dutch translations of 'Welfare Provisions'). For Good Practices, a similar filter was put in place. For Tutorials, instead, the Story can be written by any Commoner but it must have the tags 'Tutorial' and 'HowTo'.

The author of a Story can be either a Commoner or a Group, and a Story can be published anonymously. In this case the author is not visible in the Story's metadata, substituted by the word 'Anonymous', and the Story does not appear in the public profile of the author. Nevertheless, the author of the Story can always edit or delete the Story, since the relation between them is kept in the data model, only it is hidden for all the other Commoners/visitors .

The same Story can be written in four languages (English, Italian, Croatian, Dutch), regardless of the language in which the platform is used. This means that a Commoner who uses Commonfare.net in Italian can write a Story either solely in English, or both in English and Italian, or in any other possible combination of the available languages. It is important to notice that this is implemented in a way such as the Story is a unique object which has one or more relations with other objects - the translations. This has some advantages, especially because it simplifies a lot the data consistency, so that, for example, a modification to the metadata of a Story affects all its translations, or the cancellation of a Story eliminates also all its translations.

The Stories shown on the homepage are selected using their translations, such that the latest Stories which have a translation in the current platform language, defaulting on those with an English translation, are presented first. This reduces the possibility that, for example, a visitor from Croatia sees Stories written in Dutch. So, for this example, the rule is to give precedence to Stories with a Croatian translation, followed by those with an English translation.

1.2.1 Story Builder

Stories appeared on Commonfare.net in R2, and the only way Commoners had for writing Stories was through a simple WYSIWYG editor that has been customised to include images and videos, and for managing translations. Figure 6 illustrates how this editor looks like.

FIGURE 6. THE WYSIWYG EDITOR

With R3 we released a new tool for composing Stories, called Story Builder. It has not entirely replaced the WYSIWYG editor but it became the default tool for composing Stories, so the Stories that have been created using the old editor could still be accessed for editing. The Story Builder, designed by UniTN and FBK, is a free and open source component that has been built from scratch for the purposes of Commonfare.net by FBK. It can be easily reused for other projects, given that it has been developed as an independent tool to be integrated in any web application³.

The Story Builder keeps the same data model of the Story, but it changes the way the Story is composed, making the author follow some steps and allowing him/her to interact with the content in an easy and visually effective way.

A detailed description of the motivations that led to the creation of the Story Builder, along with a complete overview of its capabilities, is given in D4.1 (Sect. 5.3 and 6.1 in particular), while in this document we highlight its main technical features.

³ see <https://github.com/Commonfare-net/storybuilder-react>

FIGURE 7. THE STORY BUILDER IN ACTION

After the author has typed the title and the place, the Story Builder shows a set of possible actions for adding different types of content to the Story, as depicted in the left image of Figure 7. Each part of the Story is thus presented in the form of a block, split into two parts. The left one contains the glyph that represents the type of content (text in the example in Figure 7, third image), and the right one shows a preview of the content. Tapping (or clicking on) a block will ‘open’ it for editing its content, or for removing it (Figure 7, second image). To make the creation of a Story more interactive and flexible, especially on mobile devices, all the blocks can be reordered by dragging them up or down.

To persist Stories on Commonfare.net, the Story Builder does not use any ‘Save’ button, like the one used in the WYSIWYG editor (see bottom of Figure 6), instead it automatically saves the content of the blocks while the author creates it. This is particularly useful on small screen, as it avoids to scroll down to a button to save the modifications and up again to continue. This ‘autosave’ feature is also valid for the other parts of the Story Builder (title, place, tags) as well as for the action of moving the blocks.

Differently from what happens with the WYSIWYG editor, in which by pressing the ‘Save’ button the Story gets also published, in the Story Builder there is the possibility to create a draft of the Story before actually publishing it. All the modifications are saved in the draft, and only when the author taps/clicks on the ‘Publish’ button the Story goes public (see the right image of Figure 7). The author can also get a preview of the Story before publishing it to check how it appears for all the readers.

As said before, the Story Builder is the default tool for writing Stories on Commonfare.net, but there is still the possibility to write a Story using the WYSIWYG editor by tapping/clicking on the link in the top left part of the Story Builder (see Figure 7, left image).

1.2.2 Comments

Like on many popular online platforms, Commoners on Commonfare.net can express their opinion or contribute to discussion about a certain content by posting comments. Comments contain normal text (with automatic recognition of links), the reference to the Commoner who has posted it, and they can relate to both Stories and Listings (see next the Commoncoin section for more information about Listings). Comments can only be created by Commoners, so registration is required for commenting, and they are public, so visitors can read them.

To make clear that anybody can comment on Commonfare.net, we implemented the creation of a Comment in a way that it is possible to write a Comment without being logged in, and asking to login or register only as a last step before the actual publication.

Like a Story, a Comment can also be posted anonymously, meaning that the name of the author is hidden and replaced by the word 'Anonymous'. Even when a Comment is posted anonymously, it remains editable by its creator, since the reference between the Commoner and the Comment persists in the data model.

For both Stories and Listings, Commoner's Comments are visible after the actual content, like in many popular blogging platforms. Since R4 there is an additional section, placed between a Story and its Comments, that contains the Recommended Stories.

1.2.3 Recommended Stories

Besides the visualisation of the Commonshare in the Commoner's profile, the other visible usage of the Commonshare is inside the page that presents a Story to a reader, be it a Commoner or just a visitor. In fact, at the bottom of each Story, there are three links to Stories that Commonfare.net has identified as 'related' to the current one (see Figure 8).

FIGURE 8. AN EXAMPLE OF RECOMMENDED STORIES

The Recommended Stories are identified in real time by a custom version of the Pagerank algorithm that makes use of the Commonshare, whose details are discussed in the second part of this document, that takes two possible pieces of data as input:

- the identifier of the Story, if the reader is not logged in
- the identifier of the Story and the identifier of the Commoner if the reader is logged in

In order to ensure smooth interaction with the story while waiting for the algorithm results, the API call for retrieving the Recommended Stories is performed asynchronously after the page is loaded, and the links to the stories are added to the page as soon as the results arrive. This is a design choice that does not affect the user experience of the reader, seeing that having placed the Recommended Stories after the content of the Story allows us to fill this section without the reader noticing it.

1.3 COMMONCOIN

Commoncoin is the digital currency of Commonfare.net, that Commoners can exchange each other within the platform. Each Commoner has a wallet in Commoncoin, shown in the left image of Figure 9, that shows the current balance and the latest transactions. The Commoncoin wallet, including its balance and the list of transactions is accessible only by the Commoner who owns it.

In order to be able to exchange Commoncoin from the beginning, all the Commoners receive 1000.00 Commoncoin upon registration, that they find immediately in their Commoncoin wallet.

In order to send Commoncoins, a Commoner can use the button 'Send cc' on her/his wallet and then enter the name of the recipient and the amount to transfer, as depicted in the central image of Figure 9. To facilitate the interaction, given that the name of the Commoner can be any name and is unique, the field for the name features an autocomplete functionality that suggests the possible names that match the text the Commoner is typing. A transaction can also have a message that is visible to both the sender and the recipient.

To minimize the possibility of making mistakes that can lead to wrong transactions (such as entering the wrong amount or the wrong recipient), a transaction in Commoncoin is always performed in two steps: in fact, after having filled all the fields, the Commoner has to confirm the transaction in a page that summarises the transaction information, as shown in the right image of Figure 9.

FIGURE 9. THE COMMONCOIN WALLET (LEFT IMAGE) AND THE TRANSACTION FLOW (CENTRAL AND RIGHT IMAGES)

1.3.1 Commonplace

Commoncoins can be exchanged with any other Commoner at any time, and they can also be used for exchanging items listed in the Commonplace. The Commonplace is public section of Commonfare.net in which Commoners can create and see the Listings posted by other Commoners. At the level of data representation, a Listing is similar to a Story, as it contains:

- title
- text body
- images
- minimum and maximum price in Commoncoin
- tags
- metadata: place, author, date of creation.

The image on the left in Figure 10 shows the form for publishing a new Listing. A Listing can contain multiple images, that are all displayed as thumbnails in the Listing page once the Listing is published. By tapping/clicking on one of them, the image becomes full screen and opens a gallery for viewing the others.

FIGURE 10. CREATION OF A NEW LISTING (LEFT) AND A LISTING PAGE (RIGHT)

Differently from most of the online platforms in which people sell and buy items or services, in Commonfare.net there is no button 'Buy' or similar. In the Commonplace the only way to get an item or a service (and eventually pay in Commoncoin for it) is by getting in contact with the Commoner who published the Listing. By tapping/clicking on the 'Get in touch' button at the bottom of the Listing, in fact, a new Conversation (see Figure 2) between the two Commoners is opened with a default message about being interested in the Commonplace listing. In case a Conversation between the two Commoners already exists, then it is visualised.

Like Stories, Listings can have Comments that are visualised in the same way, with the same possibility of anonymity.

1.3.2 Basic income and implementation notes

Since R3 every Commoner receives a basic income of 1000,00 Commoncoin each month. This is a fully automated task that is executed in background every 5th of the month. In this case the 'coins' are taken from a central wallet, managed by the Consortium, that can go infinitely negative.

On Commonfare.net, the Commoncoin is managed by two entities: the platform itself and an instance of the Social Wallet⁴ that runs on the same server. The Social Wallet, described in detail in D4.2, is the tool developed by DYNE that allows to store and retrieve transactions on a database in a very fast, secure, and efficient way. For R3 DYNE has also implemented an additional layer, called Social Wallet API⁵ (SWAPI), which allows any external system to communicate with the Social

⁴ See <https://github.com/Commonfare-net/social-wallet>

⁵ See <https://github.com/Commonfare-net/social-wallet-api>

Wallet through a well documented interface. In order to be able to exchange data between Commonfare.net and the Social Wallet using the Social Wallet API, FBK has developed a generic library (namely a *Ruby Gem*) called *social-wallet-ruby*, that acts as a client for the SWAPI. This library has been bundled in Commonfare.net and it is used also for managing the Group Currencies, like Santacoin and Oltrino (©), as explained in the next section.

The way transactions work on Commonfare.net can be described as follows: when a Commoner confirms a transaction (see the right image of Figure 9) a new Transaction is instantiated on Commonfare.net; the Transaction object contains a reference to the transaction stored on the Social Wallet, so, before persisting the Transaction on Commonfare.net, the platform makes a background call to the SWAPI to create the transaction on the Social Wallet. If this succeeds, the SWAPI returns the unique identifier of this transaction, which is then persisted in the Transactions of Commonfare.net. Once it is saved, the platform makes another call to the SWAPI to update the balance of the wallet. In case the call to the SWAPI should fail, the Transaction is not persisted on Commonfare.net and an error message is shown to the Commoner.

This way, every transaction made by Commoners is stored twice and into different databases - the one of Commonfare.net and the one of the Social Wallet. Even if this may look redundant, it has advantages from the point of view of performance: doing like this, in fact, significantly reduces the number of calls to the SWAPI, which is invoked only for performing the actual transaction, and not for retrieving the list of the past ones, or to get the balance. These data are in fact stored in the database of Commonfare.net, which is faster and whose *Object-relational mapping*⁶ is already optimised by Ruby on Rails, the framework upon which the platform is built.

1.4 GROUPS

On Commonfare.net, Groups are entities that put together and in a certain way represent multiple Commoners. Any Commoner can create a Group and can be part of Groups created others, by making a request for joining an existing Group. Given that the motivations for having added Groups to Commonfare.net can be found in D4.1 (see Ch. 5 in particular), in this section we briefly describe the technical aspects of Groups and we provide the relevant information about how some features have been implemented.

A Group is a very simple entity as it has:

- name, public
- description, public
- image, public, used as the public group avatar
- at least one Membership, which represents its relation with members of the Group.

⁶ See https://guides.rubyonrails.org/active_record_basics.html#object-relational-mapping

Memberships have roles, so the role of a Commoner in the Group is stored in the related Membership. The possible roles are: Administrator, Editor, Affiliate.

- *Administrator* is the role that is automatically given to the Commoner who creates the Group, and it can be assigned to, or revoked from other members by another Administrator. A Group must always have at least one Administrator, and Administrators can do everything that the other roles can do. Administrators can also edit the Group name, description, avatar, can accept/reject join requests from Commoners, and can create and administer a Group Currency (see next section).
- *Editors* can write Stories on behalf of the Group, which means that the author that appears in the Story page is the Group instead of the Commoner.
- *Affiliates* can participate to Discussions and start new ones, and is the default role of newly accepted members.

Discussions are very similar to Conversations with the remarkable difference that any member of the Group can participate. To give an idea, Discussions are something between threads in a classic online forum and 'group chats' in many popular messaging apps like Whatsapp or Telegram. Discussions are visible only to the members of the Group and, when a new message is posted on a Discussion, all the Commoners who participate to that Discussion receive a Notification.

1.4.1 Group currency

Although Commoncoin is the currency that every Commoner can exchange, it is not the only currency that can be used in Commonfare.net. In fact, the platform is designed to use any number of currencies, thanks to the concept of the Group Currency.

In short, any Group can use their own currency, which is exchangeable only by the Group members, each of whom has a wallet for that Group Currency, in addition to the one for Commoncoin. The Group Currency is not exchangeable with Commoncoin, meaning by this that there is no mechanism implemented in the platform that allows a conversion between Commoncoin and a Group Currency. However, 'Group Coins' can be exchanged between group members, in the same way as Commoncoin: from his/her wallet in the Group Currency, in fact, the Commoner can transfer any amount (limited to the current balance) to any other member of the group.

The Group Currency is backed by an external instance of the Social Wallet and the SWAPI, protected by an API key, that someone (likely an administrator of the Group) must set up using their own resources. Commonfare.net, in fact, hosts only Commoncoin and does not provide hosting for other instances of the Social Wallet. This ensures that the control and the responsibility on the Group Currency is completely in the hands of the Group itself, and Commonfare.net becomes the interface through which the members can use it.

To facilitate the setup of the backend for the Group Currency, FBK and DYNE have created a standalone toolkit⁷, available on Github, that can be installed and run in few steps. Setting up an instance of the Social Wallet is a task that could easily be done by a person with technical skills, but may present some difficulties for non-technical people. For this reason the Consortium has provided different tutorials, all available on Commonfare.net, that explain how to set up the Group Currency and take the reader to the correct technical guides on Github.

1.5 SANTACOIN AND OLTRINO

The Group Currency has been the subject of two real world experiments during the project: in July 2018 at the Santarcangelo Festival with the *Santacoin*, and in June 2019 at the OltrEconomia Festival with the *Oltrino* (whose symbol is ©).

The Santarcangelo Festival is the longest-running Italian festival dedicated to the arts of the contemporary performing scene, and one of the most significant European events in the field of theater and dance⁸. The OltrEconomia Festival takes place in the city of Trento in parallel and in alternative to the Festival of the Economy that is held every year in late May. The OltrEconomia Festival collects the debate and bottom-up experiences that promote other possible ways for a more sustainable economy⁹. More details about the two events are given in D4.1 (Sect. 6.3) for Santacoin and D5.3 (Ch. 8) for both (other detailed reports were shared internally to the consortium), here we briefly describe the technical aspects of these two experiences.

All the work around Santacoin and Oltrino have been managed directly by members of the project Consortium, from the online/offline communication (UNITN, FBK, M-ITI, CPS) to the operations on the field (DYNE, UniTN, FBK, M-ITI), to the setup and configuration of the Group Currency (FBK). More specifically, in both cases we have created the Groups, we have set up the instances of the SWAPI used as backend for the currencies (see next section for details), and we created in advance the wallets needed for the events. The latter is one of the two main differences between these two Group Currencies and a 'standard' one. The other is the fact that for these two currencies we enabled the possibility to access the wallet using a QR code¹⁰, which allowed people to exchange Santacoin and Oltrino without being registered on the platform.

⁷ See <https://github.com/Commonfare-net/commonfare-swapi-deploy>

⁸ See <https://www.santarcangelofestival.com>

⁹ See <https://oltrconomia.info>

¹⁰ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/QR_code

For both Santarcangelo and OltrEconomia we modeled the users of the currency depending on the possible ways they would have used it, and we defined the following types of users, here explained using the Oltrino (©) as the example currency:

- The *Infopoint*, that represents the person at the place where people could get the wallets, pre-charged with fixed amounts (10©, 20©, 50©), paying them in Euro. The exchange ratio was 1Euro = 1©. The Infopoint could also re-charge the wallets and do the cash-out, i.e. give back in Euro what was left on the wallet in ©.
- The *Seller*, that represents the person in one of the places where people could spend their © for buying food and drinks, but also clothes, books, and services like hairdressing or massage (in the case of Santarcangelo).
- The *Customer*, that represents one person in the audience of the Festival who spend © at the Sellers' points.
- The *Commoner*, i.e. that represents the Customer who has 'activated' the account on Commonfare.net during the event.

To clarify what the 'activation' is, we must explain why the wallets has been generated and pre-charged in advance.

Since the expectations in terms of adoption of the © were high, we decided that asking each new person to register on the platform and join the Group would have been too complex and would have significantly slowed down the operations in case of high crowd. For these reasons we generated in advance a number of wallets, with their QR codes, each one associated to an account on the platform. These accounts had credentials and usernames that have been randomly generated. Moreover, these accounts could not be counted as a 'real' Commoners for three reasons: 1) they existed only because they were instrumental to the operations in ©, 2) not all of these accounts would have been used, 3) we expected that many of the accounts that would have been used for exchanging © would not have continued engagement with the platform.

So, in order to be able to measure how many people would have effectively joined Commonfare.net after having used the ©, we implemented the mechanism of the activation. By activating the account from the wallet page, the Customer could change the username, put his/her email, choose a password and then sign up. At this point, this person could be considered a Commoner. Figure 11 shows the © wallet of a Customer and the activation page.

FIGURE 11. THE © WALLET OF A CUSTOMER AND THE ACTIVATION PAGE

Given this context, the actors involved, and the operations they should have made, we took advantage of the Group Roles in Commonfare.net and mapped them such that we could match the needs of the experimentation: the Infopoint had the Administrator role, the Seller had the Editor role, and the Customer had no role defined in its Membership. The Affiliate role was given to those Customers who 'activated' their account.

Santacoin and Oltrino used a set of features of the Group Currency, QR codes and role mapping, that have been developed for these particular cases, and that are not yet publicly available to every Group, since they require some 'manual' work for the generation of the wallets and the QR codes. Given that the two experimentations have been successful, we now have the confidence to implement these features in a way that can be used by any Group. After the end of the project, when the recently established Commonfare Association will take the ownership of Commonfare.net, these features will be among the top priorities for the new functionalities to implement.

1.6 INTEGRATION AND DEPLOYMENT

In this section we provide a description of the different components that comprise the Commonfare platform, providing some details about the underlying technologies and how they have been integrated to work together.

FIGURE 12. ARCHITECTURE OF COMMONFARE.NET

Figure 12 depicts a high level overview of the architecture of Commonfare.net, which is composed of the following elements:

- the Rails application, which is the actual web application that manages the business logic, the views (HTML, CSS, Javascript) and the data for Commoners, Stories, Groups, Listings, Wallets, Transactions, etc. The web application is written using Rails 5, the most recent stable release of Ruby on Rails when we started with the software development¹¹. The entire source code of the Rails app is available on Github¹².
- the Commonfare database, a PostgreSQL database where all the data is persisted. It is accessible only by the Rails app and its data resides in a storage that is backed up twice per day.
- the instance of the Social Wallet and Social Wallet API that manage the backend of the Commoncoin. It is written in Closure and its source code is available on Github.
- the Commoncoin database, a MongoDB, accessible only by the Social Wallet, which stores the transactions for the Social Wallet.

¹¹ Rails 6 stable has been released at the beginning of May 2019

¹² See <https://github.com/Commonfare-net/commonfare-rails>

- The Commonsware toolkit, which does the analysis of the Commonsware and the calculations for the Recommended Stories. It is written in Python and its source code is available on Github¹³.

Each of the aforementioned elements runs as a single service inside a Docker container¹⁴, represented by the rectangle with the blue whale¹⁵ in Figure 12, that isolates it from the other components and ensures that each of them is executed independently in a self-contained environment. However, all the services run together using a tool called 'Docker Compose'¹⁶, represented by the external box in Figure 12, which creates a virtual network through which they can communicate and ensures that they all start/stop together. All the services are not visible from the outside, apart from the Rails application, which is the one that actually responds to the HTTP requests made to the address *commonfare.net*.

Using Docker and Docker Compose simplifies both the development and the deployment of the whole system, as they guarantee that consistency is kept between the different working environments (development, staging, production).

During the periods in which Santacoin and Oltrino have been used, the respective services were running inside the same instance of Docker Compose, on the same server at FBK, along with those mentioned before. Another advantage of using such an architecture is, in fact, that single services can be switched on and off when it is needed and without affecting any of the others.

1.6.1 Group Currency architecture

Figure 13 depicts how the architecture of Commonfare looks like when using an external Group Currency.

¹³ See <https://github.com/Commonfare-net/commonshare>

¹⁴ See <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container>

¹⁵ The blue whale with containers on its back is the logo of Docker

¹⁶ See <https://docs.docker.com/compose/>

FIGURE 13. COMMONFARE WITH GROUP CURRENCY

The part on the left represents what is illustrated in Figure 12 (to simplify the drawing we kept only the Rails part) and the right part represents the Social Wallet with its MongoDB, both running as Docker containers inside their instance of Docker Compose. This way the two systems run completely isolated one from the other, typically on different servers, but they can communicate and exchange data using the Social Wallet API through the Internet, as explained in the Group Currency section.

1.7 RELEASES

In line with the schedule of the PIE News/Commonfare project, the platform has been rolled out through different main incremental releases. Details of the work carried out for R1 and R2 have already been provided in D4.1, where R3 and R4 have been described only in terms of design. In this section, instead, we give details about the work of implementation done for R3 and R4, listing the main features that have been added to the platform. All the details about the evolution of the code can be found in the commit history on the Github repository of Commonfare.net¹⁷.

1.7.1 Release 3

What follows is a list of the work that has been done throughout Task 4.4 that led to R3. For brevity, we use the generic term *implementation* for the work of design, development, and test of the data model, the business logic, and the presentation of the relative item. The items are not in chronological order, but rather grouped by topic. All the work has been done in short iterations, two

¹⁷ See <https://github.com/Commonfare-net/commonfare-rails/commits/master>

weeks to one month of duration, avoiding as much as possible a *waterfall* approach, thus preferring an *agile* one, a software project management methodology that better copes with the requirements of evolutive platforms like Commonfare.net.

- Implementation of *social-wallet-ruby*, the Ruby Gem for consuming the API of the SWAPI
- Implementation of Wallets with the needed automated actions (initial income, give back on Commoner's cancellation), one wallet per Commoner with polymorphic association to support Group Wallets
- Implementation of Transactions, with authorisations and validations (amount limited to current balance, no self-transactions, etc.); implementation of the confirmation mechanism
- Implementation of Groups and Memberships, and the related authorisations.
- Implementation of Join Requests for groups, based on a simple finite state machine for managing the status changes and the relative actions
- Implementation of a mechanism of leaving a Group keeping consistency with other group elements like discussions and transactions in the group currency
- Possibility to create a Group immediately after registration
- Possibility to publish Stories as a Group
- Implementation of the Discussions between Group members, with the related authorisations
- Implementation of the Conversations between Commoners, with the related authorisations
- Implementation of Messages, used by both Discussions and Conversations, and implemented using polymorphism to be dynamically associated with them.
- Implementation of the Story Builder, in several iterations, as a standalone Javascript tool
- Integration of the Story Builder in the platform
- Implementation of the Story Builder templates
- Implementation of the Commonplace
- Implementation of Listings, with the relative authorisations, associations with Comments and Conversations.
- Implementation of Notifications, with the relative authorisations and lifecycle
- Possibility of starting a Comment without being registered.
- Implementation of the basic income and the relative automation
- Implementation of the Metrics Dashboard, a section of Commonfare.net that provides indicators about the status of the platform, such as the number of Commoners, the number of visitors, the most searched keywords and the Social Graph. The latter is a dynamic visualisation of the interactions between Commoners, Stories and Listings, calculated using the Commonshare Toolkit (see section 2).
- Continuous improvements and fixes to the overall UI/UX for Stories, Profile, Listings, Comments, Home page, Wallets, etc., carried out in multiple iterations.

1.7.2 Release 4 and Final release

What follows is a list of the work that has been done in Task 4.[REF] of WP4 for arriving to R4. The same considerations about terminology and approach used in the previous section are valid for R4.

- Improvements to the Notification system, especially for Comments
- Improvements to the Conversations and Discussions
- Implementation of the mechanism for automatically setting the language of the home page without accessing the IP address of the visitor
- Implementation of the role management for Groups
- Improvements to the social-wallet-ruby Gem to be aligned with the new releases of the SWAPI by DYNE
- Integration of the Commonshare toolkit developed by AU. This included the 'Dockerization' of the whole system and the automation of the tasks that
 - a. extract the data from the platform database
 - b. trigger the analysis of the Commonshare
 - c. retrieve the results for each Commoner and persists it in the platform database
- Implementation of the Commonshare visualization in the Commoner's profile, done with the support of both UniTN and AU
- Implementation of the mechanism for retrieving the Recommended Stories on the platform side.
- Possibility to make Tutorials to support T2.3.
- Merge of the Good Practices into the Commoners Voices
- Implementation of the Group Currency and QR code functionality, initially only for Santarcangelo, then made available to all Groups
- Improvements to the 'QR code enabled' Group Currencies, tested with the Oltrino. This included
 - a. the possibility to associate the QR code enabled wallet to an existing account on the platform, independently from being already logged-in or not
 - b. improvements to wallet's security, by means of a stronger authorisation and an additional layer of protection
- Improvements to the Metrics Dashboard, replacement of the most searched keywords with the most popular Stories
- Continuous improvements and fixes to the overall UI/UX for Stories, Profile, Listings, Comments, Home page, Wallets, etc., carried out in multiple iterations.

2. THE COMMONSHARE TOOLKIT

Participatory design research conducted in WP3 and described in D3.1 and 3.2 demonstrated that potential users of Commonfare.net wish to be acknowledged for their contributions to the platform and not for the delivery of a service, such that each user creates and owns a share of the common value being created through these contributions. Hence, this shared value is referred to as **commonsare (see D3.2 for the underlying design proposition and related research)**, which is the individual share of the wider common good created by the community within the platform. The research/development problem that arose was then to design and implement a novel metric capable of capturing and conveying the user contribution to the common good. Here, elements of social network analysis are introduced before a description of the initial algorithm upon which the commonsare calculation is based, and modifications that have been made to account for characteristics of Commonfare.net itself.

For analysis purposes, Commonfare.net can be considered as a social network platform where user interactions are mediated by their content such as stories and listings. A suitable representation for this network must satisfy the following requirements:

1. It should capture the dynamics by which the Commonfare.net community creates and accesses the common wealth of content shared online.
2. It should clearly illustrate the users and content that most strongly contribute to the cohesion, sustainability and growth of the platform.

By modelling the network as a dynamic graph, this captures the emergence of aggregated complex dynamics formed from local interactions at the user level. As described in D3.2 this also responds to a novel theoretical directions for the design of online reputations, which embraces Assemblage Theory and Actor-Network Theory (ANT). Theory reasoning underpinning the approach is also described in D3.2. High-level insights into community activity can be inferred from actions such as creating and sharing stories, leaving comments on stories, or replying to such comments (as well as the order in which these actions are taken). These actions are logged to allow reconstruction of dynamics between Commoners and their content, this producing a view of the commonsare collective. This in turn allows for online reputation to be modelled upon the relation individual-collectivity.

The evolving graph model consists of two sets of nodes: the set of contents, and the set of Commoners, both considered as actants from an ANT perspective, creating in fact a hybrid collective. New contents are created, and new Commoners join the platform, causing these sets to grow over time. We assume an initial set of contents and Commoners exist at the beginning. When Commoner A posts a new story, she is the owner and a link exists a priori between her and this

story. If another Commoner B leaves a comment, a link will be created between B and the story. Further, a third link will be created between Commoners A and B, since these users have indirectly interacted with one another through the medium of A's created content. Links between Commoners can also be created irrespective of content, through conversations or transactions. These interaction types, and the direction they exist in, are illustrated in Figure 14 (top part of the figure). This node-link graph structure of interactions can be exploited to determine each Commoner's influence in the network.

There are several such methods to determine how influential (central) a node is, some of which are referenced in Figure 15. A review of centrality measures which could be used for the research was provided in D3.1 and the rationale behind the choice of the K-core metrics was presented in D3.2. For Commonfare.net, however, the coreness metric is applied to compute centrality. The advantage of this metric is that it connects an individual to a global structural property of the assemblage as opposed to a local one, providing an accurate measure of a node's influence and allowing for an assemblage-based approach to reputation. Computation of the commonshare is based on an algorithm for determining each node's coreness, described as follows.

Algorithm 1: The Batagelj and Zaversnik algorithm for k -core decomposition

Data: graph $G = (V, E)$
Result: table $core[v]$ contains the k -coreness of $v \in V$

```

1 Init: Order  $V$  by  $degree[v]$  for all  $v \in V$ ;
2 for  $v \in V$  do
3    $core[v] \leftarrow degree[v]$ ;
4   for  $u \in neighbours[v]$  do
5     if  $degree[u] > degree[v]$  then
6        $degree[u] \leftarrow degree[u] - 1$ ;
7       reorder  $V$  accordingly;

```

FIGURE 14. COMMONFARE INTERACTIONS FOR COMPUTATION OF THE COMMONSHARE (TOP) AND K-CORE ALGORITHM (BOTTOM)

Centrality measure	Formula
Degree: Node is directly connected to many others	$C_D(p_k) = \sum_{i=1}^n a(p_i, p_k)$
Betweenness: Node is on many communication paths	$C_B(p_k) = \sum_{i \neq j \neq k} \frac{g_{ij}(p_k)}{g_{ij}}$
Closeness: Node is near many others in the network	$C_C(p_k) = \frac{n-1}{\sum_{i=1}^n d(p_i, p_k)}$

FIGURE 15. CENTRALITY MEASURES

An individual's contribution to Commonfare.net is primarily based on their core number within a k-core decomposition of the aforementioned interaction network. A k-core is a maximal subgraph (the largest subgraph in which all nodes are reachable from each other) that consists of nodes with a degree of at least k. The core number of a node is the largest value k of a k-core containing that node. Its computation in Commonfare.net employs a Python implementation of an algorithm introduced by Batagelj and Zaversnik¹⁸, which is included in the NetworkX Python package. The O(m) complexity of this algorithm (where m is the number of edges) enables rapid calculation for all nodes in the network. Pseudocode for this decomposition algorithm can be seen in Algorithm 1, with an example k-core decomposition illustrated in Figure 14 (on the left of the algorithm). As this figure shows, an advantage of the core number metric is that it considers a node's influence with respect to the global graph structure, as opposed to a localised measure of influence, such as degree. As such, the k-core decomposition method can be applied to identify influential members of social networks - an approach that has been verified in previous work. The node's core number is therefore justified as a base measure of its impact in the interaction network of Commonfare.net, and thereby the commonshare of the Commoner whom it represents.

2.1 MODIFICATIONS FOR DYNAMIC, WEIGHTED NETWORKS

The original k-core decomposition algorithm shown in Algorithm 1 (Figure 14, bottom part) accounts for neither the difference in weight of interactions between entities, nor the dynamic nature of a social network where interactions exist at different points in time and may disappear and reappear as time passes. For calculating the resultant weighted k-core, a similar calculation is used to that in previous work by Garas et al (2012)¹⁹. The weighting of nodes in the Commonfare.net network is based on the following heuristic principles (they are not guaranteed to yield optimal values, but instead serve as practical guidelines):

¹⁸ Batagelj, V. and Zaversnik, M. (2011). Fast algorithms for determining (generalized) core groups in social networks. *Advances in Data Analysis and Classification*, 5(2), 129–145

¹⁹ Garas A., Schweitzer F., and Havlin, S. (2012). A k-shell decomposition method for weighted networks. *New Journal of Physics* 14, 8 (Aug 2012), 083030. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/14/8/083030>

1. Interaction types may be weighted differently: In Commonfare.net, interactions are diverse in nature, from transferring digital currency to leaving a comment on a story. Each interaction is given a weight in both directions. As these are estimates of significance, they are not optimal and in future, Commoners themselves should decide on the significance of interactions.
2. Interaction weights decrease over time: As a dynamic network, Commoners' level of contribution at a particular point in time is dependent on how recent their interactions took place. From an Assemblage Theory perspective, Commoners have social mobility on Commonfare.net that does not constrain them to a geographically close group or "territory". Links are thus easier to form but require continued effort to maintain their strength.
3. Repeated interactions decrease in weight: The growth of Commonfare.net relies on Commoners establishing new interactions. While multiple interactions increase the weight of an edge between nodes, subsequent interactions along the same edge decrease in value. For example, we assume that a Commoner who leaves five comments on a story does not make five times the contribution of one who leaves a single comment. While again this is an assumption based on intuition, its main purpose is to reduce the impact from potentially collusive behavior.

2.2 SUMMARY

With these modifications, we operated to the efficient k-core decomposition algorithm account for the weighted, directed, dynamic properties of Commonfare.net platform interactions. Fair calculation of the reputation of platform users is highly important for understanding and encouraging further platform use. Our collaboration-oriented reputation system - the commonshare - offers a new perspective on online reputation distinct from individualistic, competitive aspects of traditional approaches and is aligned with the ethos and practices of the commonfare.net platform. The users' commonshare aim to encourage active participation and collaboration in Commonfare.net, while the use of social network analysis to derive this metric allows platform administrators to understand the dynamics of platform contributions, and how to encourage participation. The commonshare certainly aims to contribute to the sustainability of the platform overtime by providing a metrics upon which users can relate to understand their contribution and other users' contribution to the common good. Moreover, we believe that the commonshare implementation could become particularly relevant to administrators of other platforms that support mutual collaboration. The toolkit indeed could be transferable to other experiences wishing to test with this new metric and design. The following section describes the implementation of these principles, as well as general implementation of the commonshare calculation process. Work on the modification and implementation started in May 2018 and was led by partner Abertay.

2.3 IMPLEMENTATION

FIGURE 16. GEXF FOR THE COMMONSHARE

This section briefly details the implementation of the processing pipeline employed for the commonshare calculation - beginning with a GEXF (Graph Exchange XML Format) file and ending with a series of JSON files for visualisation purposes. Presently, graph files that are in other formats (such as GraphML, DOT or CSV) are imported into Gephi, a graph visualisation platform, and exported into the required GEXF format. Thus, this approach can be used for any graph format supported by Gephi.

Figure 17. Commonshare k-core decomposition

2.4 PRELIMINARY PARSING

To be read by the scripts for commonshare calculation and JSON graph generation, the GEXF file must conform to certain constraints, described as follows and illustrated in Figure 17a.

Removal of loops - For the k-core calculation to operate correctly, all edges where the source node is also the target are removed. Given that the premise of commonsense is based on one's interactions with others in a social network, it should not be possible to accumulate reputation by interacting with oneself.

Merging of bi-directional edges - Parallel edges must be reduced to a single edge, while retaining the attributes of both edges. For example, an edge from a node x to another node y may have a different 'weight' to that of the edge from y to x. To differentiate the two, the source node ID is appended onto the value of the attribute, delimited by a forward slash. Figure 16 graphically demonstrates the change in node-edge structure alongside changes to the underlying GEXF.

Dynamic subgraph generation - To understand the dynamic nature of network activity, an interval is chosen on which to segment the entire timestamped graph into windowed snapshots. In the case of Commonfare.net, a two-week interval is used, such that sub-graphs are generated for every two-week period of activity, with no overlap of these two-week windows.

Timestamp filtering (Figure 17b) - As shown in the lower half of Figure 16, "spell" attributes are appended to edges (as well as nodes) that represent the time periods in which they existed. Each edge and node must have a spell start or end that exists in the window, otherwise it is removed.

Irrelevant edge removal (Figure 17c) - In the case of Commonfare.net, all edges that connect Commoners or stories to their tags are not indicative of a contribution and therefore must be removed to avoid influencing the k-core algorithm. At this point, the degree of each node can be calculated.

Node weighting (Figure 17d) - In addition to the node's degree, each node is given a weight based on the attributes of their edges, thereby distinguishing it from the original k-core algorithm. For each edge, the following may be present in a network dataset for determining edge weight:

1. **No additional information:** This is often the case in existing datasets, which simply document that an edge exists between two nodes with no further information.
2. **A "weight" edge attribute:** Network datasets may include an explicit edge weight attribute. For example, in trust networks, this weight corresponds to the source node's trust ranking of the target node.
3. **Number of parallel edges:** During the preliminary parsing phase, the number of times either node initiated an interaction is stored. When no other information is present, this number is used as a proxy for the edge's weight.
4. **Weighted action type attributes:** In the case of Commonfare.net, an edge weight can be inferred by the actions between nodes that it represents. Algorithm 2 shows the process by which this weight is calculated.

Algorithm 2: Calculating the weight of a node based on its interactions

Data: graph G , node N , start date D_0 , end date D_1
Result: weight of N , from period $D_0 \dots D_1$

```

1 Init:  $W \leftarrow []$ ;
2 for  $edge \in G.edges$  do
3    $dep_m \leftarrow 1, w \leftarrow 0$ ;
4   for  $action \leftarrow edge.actions$  do
5      $age \leftarrow \mathbf{dateDiff}(action.date, D_1)$ ;
6      $dep_a \leftarrow e^{-0.01 * age}$ ;
7      $w \leftarrow w + (action.weight * dep_a * dep_m)$ ;
8      $dep_m = dep_m * 0.75$ ;
9    $W.append(w)$ ;
10 return  $\sum W$ ;

```

FIGURE 18. ALGORITHM FOR WEIGHTED CALCULATION USED FOR COMMONSHARE

In lines 5 and 6 of this algorithm, the age of the action is determined, and the age depreciation factor dep_a is calculated. The weight of the action is then reduced by dep_a and the multiple depreciation factor dep_m , which reduces the weight of recurring interactions by 75% each time. Each node's degree (d_0) is then adjusted by its edge weight sum (W), giving $d = \max(0, W \sqrt{d_0})$. An edge cannot be allocated a negative degree but decreases towards 0 over time.

K-core decomposition (Figure 17e) - The standard k-core decomposition algorithm described in Algorithm 1 is then applied to the weighted subgraph, which returns the core number of each node. Each node's core number is then normalised to a value between 1 and 10 for simplicity of representation, which represents the Commoner's commonshare. Finally, each subgraph is output as a separate JSON file. JSON files are also generated for each Commoner, containing their ego-centric subgraph for each time period. Finally, a JSON file is output for the aggregated graph of all interactions. In this graph, the steps taken to calculate a node's overall commonshare are identical to those in the aforementioned subgraph generation, with additional steps based on two aggregated activity heuristics:

1. A Commoner's overall commonshare is proportional to their weeks of activity: All else being equal, Commoners who have been consistently active for the duration of Commonfare.net have a stronger reputation than those with one or two weeks of intense activity.
2. A Commoner's overall commonshare is proportional to the subsequent activity of users whom they interact with: This principle takes the consequent influence of interactions into consideration - interactions with Commoners that do not generate any further activity should be weighted less than interactions with those that continue to participate in the platform.

The first metric, periods of activity (A), is simply a count of how many subgraphs a node existed in. The second metric, neighbourly activity (B), is edge-determinant, and represents the fraction of weeks a node's neighbour N was active following their first interaction. The weight of an edge to N is then amended as follows: $w_N \leftarrow w_N \times \min((1.3^B - 1)\sqrt{A} + 0.1, 1)$. Every edge weight will be equally influenced by the overall activity of the node in question (A), but also influenced by the neighbour's subsequent activity (B). The min function assures that the edge's weight is never increased by the adjustment. Further, an edge's weight is at least 0.1 (when B=0). The resultant commonshare distribution is log-normal, as shown in Figure 19 (left). A Box-Cox transformation is then applied to the data to yield a more normal distribution, giving the output shown in Figure 19 (middle). These transformed values can then be normalised to discrete integer values between 1 and 10, as performed for the periodic subgraphs.

FIGURE 19. NORMALISATION OF THE COMMONSHARE

Finally, work was conducted by Abertay for producing interface visualisation for representing the commonshare the end users (as seen in Figure 1 of this Deliverable). The specific design work for the visualisation is described in D5.3. Visualisation were implemented specifically using the D3 Javascript library.

2.5 PLATFORM INTEGRATION

The integration of the Commonshare toolkit in Commonfare.net has followed an evolution from a manual data export to an automated mechanism, implemented within the architecture described in section 1.6. In the first phase of the development that took to R3, in fact, data from the platform were manually extracted by FBK and sent to AU for the analysis, whose output was a dataset formatted in JSON which was sent back to FBK to be manually imported into the platform to be

displayed in the Metrics dashboard. This approach was not sustainable in the long term, but it allowed us to release the Metrics Dashboard as soon as it was ready.

After M22, when R3 has been finalised, AU and FBK started the development of the actual toolkit for the Commonshare, which consists of a Docker image (see section 1.6) as a container for the logic and the algorithms for the calculation of the Commonshare, as well as the API for exchanging that data. Moreover, FBK implemented and deployed a set of automated scripts, executed by the Rails application, that run at specified intervals to input the latest data to the Commonshare toolkit, to retrieve the results and to store them in the database. These scripts are executed every night, when the traffic on the platform is at its lowest, in order to minimize the impact that a heavy consumption of computing resources may have on the user experience.